

Supplementary Material for

Species Tree Estimation and the Impact of Extensive Gene Loss

Following Whole-Genome Duplication

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THE PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF GENE TREES FOR THE SPECIES TREE WITH GENE LOSS

We assume that a whole-genome duplication (WGD) occurs in the ancestral population at the root of a pectinate 4-taxon species tree $((A, B), C), D)$ (Fig. S1a) or a symmetric species tree $((A, B), (C, D))$ (Fig. S2a). Let t_i ($i = 2, \dots, 7$) be the length of branch i of the species tree, and t_1 is the duplication time (Fig. S1a and Fig. S2a). One of an ohnolog pair within post-WGD species is lost at a rate λ_i in the branch i ($i = 1, \dots, 7$) of the species tree (Fig. S1a and Fig. S2a). Without gene loss, two sets of orthologs (i.e., $\{A_1, B_1, C_1, D_1\}$ and $\{A_2, B_2, C_2, D_2\}$) evolve independently along the lineages of the species tree. The genealogy of 8 gene copies $\{A_1, B_1, C_1, D_1, A_2, B_2, C_2, D_2\}$ is a coalescent gene tree generated from the 8-taxon tree (Fig. S1b and Fig. S2b) under the multispecies coalescent model (MSC). If gene loss has occurred in the branches of the species tree, the genealogy of retained gene copies follows a coalescence process in a subtree of the 8-taxon tree by pruning the branches leading to the lost copies. For example, if a gene copy (i.e., the red copy in Fig. S1a and Fig. S2a) is lost at the root of the species tree, the genealogy of retained copies $\{A_2, B_2, C_2, D_2\}$ follows a coalescence process along the lineages of

the subtree T_1 (Fig. S1c and Fig. S2c) obtained by pruning the branches of the lost copies $\{A_1, B_1, C_1, D_1\}$ in the 8-taxon tree (Fig. S1b and Fig. S2b). Various combinations of gene loss in the branches of the species tree result in eight different subtrees (T_1, \dots, T_8) (Fig. S1c and Fig. S2c). Note that the subtree T_1 is identical with the species tree S . Let $P(\mathbf{G}|T_i, \theta)$ be the coalescent probability of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given the subtree T_i and population size parameters θ (see section A). Let $P(T_i|S, \lambda)$ be the probability of the subtree T_i induced by the loss process in the species tree S with loss rates λ (see section B). The probability $P(\mathbf{G}|S, \theta, \lambda)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given the species tree S (topology and branch lengths), the population size parameters θ , and the loss rates $\lambda = \{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_7\}$ (Fig. S1a and Fig. S2a) is given by

$$P(\mathbf{G}|S, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|T_i, \theta)P(T_i|S, \lambda) \quad (1)$$

A. The coalescent distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|S, \theta)$ of gene trees given the species tree S

A.1 The pectinate 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S1a)

In this section, we find the coalescent probability $P(\mathbf{G}|S, \theta)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given the pectinate 4-taxon species tree S and population size parameters θ . The result derived in this section can be used to calculate the probability $P(\mathbf{G}|T_i, \theta)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given a pectinate 4-taxon subtree T_i and population size parameters θ . There are 15 different topologies for a 4-taxon gene tree, namely, $g_1 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $g_2 = (((A, B), D), C)$, $g_3 = (((A, C), B), D)$, $g_4 = (((A, C), D), B)$, $g_5 = (((A, D), B), C)$, $g_6 = (((A, D), C), B)$, $g_7 = (((B, C), A), D)$, $g_8 = (((B, C), D), A)$, $g_9 = (((B, D), A), C)$, $g_{10} = (((B, D), C), A)$, $g_{11} = (((C, D), A), B)$, $g_{12} = (((C, D), B), A)$, $g_{13} = ((A, B), (C, D))$, $g_{14} = ((A, C), (B, D))$, $g_{15} = ((A, D), (B, C))$. Let $[x_1, x_2, x_3]$ be the number of coalescence events in the three ancestral populations of the species

tree \mathcal{S} . The lengths of the two internal branches of the species tree \mathcal{S} are denoted by w_1 and w_2 (in coalescent units), e.g., $w_1 = t_3/\theta_3$ and $w_2 = t_2/\theta_2$ where t_2 and t_3 are the lengths of two internal branches of the species tree (Fig. S1c). When the topology of the species tree is pectinate (Fig. S1a), the number of coalescence events in the first ancestral population should be either zero or one, i.e., $x_1 = 0$ or 1 , and for the second ancestral population, $x_2 = 0, 1$, or 2 . Thus, the number of coalescence events in the three ancestral populations should be $[0,0,3]$, $[0,1,2]$, $[0,2,1]$, $[1,0,2]$, or $[1,1,1]$. The probability of $[0,0,3]$ can be derived from the coalescent model, i.e.,

$$P(0,0,3) = e^{-w_1}e^{-3w_2},$$

Similarly, the probability of $[0,1,2]$ is given by

$$P(0,1,2) = e^{-w_1} \left(\frac{3}{2} e^{-w_2} (1 - e^{-2w_2}) \right).$$

The probability of $[0,2,1]$ is given by

$$P(0,2,1) = e^{-w_1} \left(1 - e^{-3w_2} - \frac{3}{2} e^{-w_2} (1 - e^{-2w_2}) \right).$$

The probability of $[1,0,2]$ is given by

$$P(1,0,2) = (1 - e^{-w_1})e^{-w_2}.$$

The probability of $[1,1,1]$ is given by

$$P(1,1,1) = (1 - e^{-w_1})(1 - e^{-w_2}).$$

If all 3 coalescent events occur at the root of the subtree, i.e., $[0,0,3]$, the probability of gene tree $g_1 = (((A, B), C), D)$ is $\frac{1}{18}$. For other scenarios $[0,1,2]$, $[0,2,1]$, $[1,0,2]$, $[1,1,1]$, the probability of gene tree g_1 is $\frac{1}{9}$, $\frac{1}{3}$, $\frac{1}{3}$, and 1 , respectively. Thus, the coalescent probability of g_1 is given by

$$P(g_1|\mathcal{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,2,1) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2) + P(1,1,1).$$

Similarly, the probability of $g_2 = (((A, B), D), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_2|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2).$$

The probability of $g_3 = (((A, C), B), D)$ is given by

$$P(g_3|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,2,1).$$

The probability of the gene tree $g_4 = (((A, C), D), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_4|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2).$$

The probability of $g_5 = (((A, D), B), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_5|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_6 = (((A, D), C), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_6|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_7 = (((B, C), A), D)$ is given by

$$P(g_7|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,2,1).$$

The probability of $g_8 = (((B, C), D), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_8|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2).$$

The probability of $g_9 = (((B, D), A), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_9|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{10} = (((B, D), C), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_{10}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{11} = (((C, D), A), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_{11}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{12} = (((C, D), B), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_{12}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{13} = ((A, B), (C, D))$ is given by

$$P(g_{13}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2).$$

The probability of $g_{14} = ((A, C), (B, D))$ is given by

$$P(g_{14}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2).$$

The probability of $g_{15} = ((A, D), (B, C))$ is given by

$$P(g_{15}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{9}P(0,1,2).$$

A.2 The symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a)

The result derived in this section can be used to calculate the probability $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given a symmetric 4-taxon subtree \mathbf{T}_i and population size parameters θ . When the topology of the species tree \mathbf{S} is symmetrical (Fig. S2a), the number of coalescence events in the three ancestral populations of the species tree \mathbf{S} should be $[0,0,3]$, $[0,1,2]$, $[1,0,2]$, or $[1,1,1]$.

The corresponding probabilities are given by $P(0,0,3) = e^{-w_1}e^{-w_2}$, $P(0,1,2) = e^{-w_1}(1 - e^{-w_2})$, $P(1,0,2) = (1 - e^{-w_1})e^{-w_2}$, and $P(1,1,1) = (1 - e^{-w_1})(1 - e^{-w_2})$. Thus, the probability of $g_1 = (((A, B), C), D)$ is given by

$$P(g_1|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2).$$

The probability of $g_2 = (((A, B), D), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_2|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2).$$

The probability of $g_3 = (((A, C), B), D)$ is given by

$$P(g_3|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_4 = (((A, C), D), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_4|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_5 = (((A, D), B), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_5|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_6 = (((A, D), C), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_6|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_7 = (((B, C), A), D)$ is given by

$$P(g_7|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_8 = (((B, C), D), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_8|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_9 = (((B, D), A), C)$ is given by

$$P(g_9|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{10} = (((B, D), C), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_{10}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{11} = (((C, D), A), B)$ is given by

$$P(g_{11}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,1,2).$$

The probability of $g_{12} = (((C, D), B), A)$ is given by

$$P(g_{12}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{1}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,1,2).$$

The probability of $g_{13} = ((A, B), (C, D))$ is given by

$$P(g_{13}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3) + \frac{1}{3}P(0,1,2) + \frac{1}{3}P(1,0,2) + P(1,1,1).$$

The probability of $g_{14} = ((A, C), (B, D))$ is given by

$$P(g_{14}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

The probability of $g_{15} = ((A, D), (B, C))$ is given by

$$P(g_{15}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \frac{2}{18}P(0,0,3).$$

B. The probability $P(T_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$ of the subtree T_i

B.1 The pectinate 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S1a)

Since the waiting time until the next gene loss is an exponential random variable with rate λ_i , the probability that a gene copy is lost in the branch i is $p_i = 1 - e^{-\tau_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 7$, where $\tau_i = \lambda_i t_i$ and t_i is the length of the branch i (Fig. S1a). There are two gene copies (red and green in Fig. S1a) in each branch of the species tree. Let p_i^r for $i = 1, \dots, 7$ be the probability that the red copy is lost in the branch i , and $(1 - p_i^r)$ is the probability that the green copy is lost in the branch i . Various combinations of gene loss in the branches of the pectinate 4-taxon species tree may result in eight subtrees, i.e., $\mathbf{T}_1 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $\mathbf{T}_2 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $\mathbf{T}_3 = (((A, B), D), C)$, $\mathbf{T}_4 = (((A, C), D), B)$, $\mathbf{T}_5 = (((B, C), D), A)$, $\mathbf{T}_6 = ((A, B), (C, D))$, $\mathbf{T}_7 = ((A, C), (B, D))$, and $\mathbf{T}_8 = ((A, D), (B, C))$ (Fig. S1c). If all 4 red copies of the first major subclade are lost or retained, the corresponding subtree is \mathbf{T}_1 (Fig. S1c). All 4 red copies are lost or retained if a loss occurs at the root (i.e., branch 1) of the species tree with probability p_1 , or if the red copies in the branch 2 and 7 are lost with probability $p_2^r p_7^r (1 - p_1) p_2 p_7$, or if the green copies in the branch 2 and 7 are lost with probability $(1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_7^r)(1 - p_1) p_2 p_7$, or if the red copies in the branch 3, 6, and 7 are lost with probability $p_3^r p_6^r p_7^r (1 - p_1)(1 - p_2) p_3 p_6 p_7$, or if the green copies in the branch 3, 6, and 7 are lost with probability $(1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)(1 - p_1)(1 - p_2) p_3 p_6 p_7$, or if the red copies in the branch 4, 5, 6, 7 are lost with probability $p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r (1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3) p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7$, or if the green copies in the branch 4, 5, 6, 7 are lost with probability $(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)(1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3) p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7$. Thus, the probability of \mathbf{T}_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= p_1 + [p_2^r p_7^r + (1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)p_2 p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_3^r p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3 p_6 p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

The subtree \mathbf{T}_2 (Fig. S1c) is obtained if three red copies (A, B, C) are lost while the red copy D is retained or if the red copy D is lost but the other 3 copies are retained. Thus, the probability of the subtree \mathbf{T}_2 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_2|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_2^r(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_2^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)p_2 p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_3^r p_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3 p_6 p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_3|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_3^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + (1 - p_3^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3 p_6 p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_4^r p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_4|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_5|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_3^r(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_3^r)p_6^r p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3 p_6 p_7 \\
&\quad + [(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4 p_5 p_6 p_7 \quad (7)
\end{aligned}$$

$$P^*(\mathbf{T}_7|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (8)$$

$$P^*(\mathbf{T}_8|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r p_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (9)$$

Since gene loss must occur such that only one gene copy is retained for each species, the probability of the subtree \mathbf{T}_i should be normalized by the probability of only one gene copy being retained for each species, which is equal to the sum $c = \sum_{i=1}^8 P^*(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$, i.e.,

$$P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = \frac{P^*(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)}{c} \quad (10)$$

B.2 The symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a)

Gene loss in the branches of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree produces 8 subtrees, i.e., $\mathbf{T}_1 = (((A, B), (C, D)), \mathbf{T}_2 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $\mathbf{T}_3 = (((A, B), D), C)$, $\mathbf{T}_4 = ((A, (C, D)), B)$, $\mathbf{T}_5 = ((B, (C, D)), A)$, $\mathbf{T}_6 = ((A, B), (C, D))$, $\mathbf{T}_7 = ((A, C), (B, D))$, and $\mathbf{T}_8 = ((A, D), (B, C))$. Note that the 8 subtrees T_i for the symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2c) are different from those for the pectinate 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2c). If all 4 red copies of the first major subclade in the symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. 2a) are lost or retained, the corresponding subtree is \mathbf{T}_1 (Fig. S2c). All 4 red copies are lost or retained if a loss occurs at the root (i.e., branch 1) of the species tree with probability p_1 , or if the red copies in the branch 2 and 3 are lost with probability $p_2^r p_3^r (1 - p_1) p_2 p_3$, or if the green copies in the branch 2 and 3 are lost with probability $(1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_1) p_2 p_3$, or if the red copies in the branch 2, 6, 7 are lost with probability $p_2^r p_6^r p_7^r (1 - p_1)(1 - p_3) p_2 p_6 p_7$, or if the green copies in the branch 2, 6, 7 are lost with probability $(1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)(1 - p_1)(1 - p_3) p_2 p_6 p_7$, or if the red copies in the branch 3, 4, 5 are lost with probability $p_3^r p_4^r p_5^r (1 - p_1)(1 - p_2) p_3 p_4 p_5$, or if the green copies in the

branch 3, 4, 5 are lost with probability $(1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3p_4p_5$, or if the red copies in the branch 4, 5, 6, 7 are lost with probability $p_4^rp_5^rp_6^rp_7^r(1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7$, or if the green copies in the branch 4, 5, 6, 7 are lost with probability $(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)(1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7$. Thus, the probability of \mathbf{T}_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= p_1 + [p_2^rp_3^r + (1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_3^r)](1 - p_1)p_2p_3 \\
&\quad + [p_2^rp_6^rp_7^r + (1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_3)p_2p_6p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_3^rp_4^rp_5^r + (1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3p_4p_5 \\
&\quad + [p_4^rp_5^rp_6^rp_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

The subtree \mathbf{T}_2 is obtained if three red copies (A, B, C) are lost while the red copy D is retained or if the red copy D is lost but the other 3 copies are retained (Fig. S2c). Thus, the probability of the subtree \mathbf{T}_2 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_2|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_2^rp_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_2^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_3)p_2p_6p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_4^rp_5^rp_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (12)
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_3|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_2^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + (1 - p_2^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_2p_6p_7 \\
&\quad + [p_4^rp_5^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (13)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_4|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_3^rp_4^r(1 - p_5^r) + (1 - p_3^r)(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3p_4p_5 \\
&\quad + [p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)p_6^rp_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_5|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_3^r(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r + (1 - p_3^r)p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)p_3p_4p_5 \\
&\quad + [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^rp_6^rp_7^r + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [p_2^r(1 - p_3^r) + (1 - p_2^r)p_3^r](1 - p_1)p_2p_3 \\
&\quad + [(1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)p_6^rp_7^r + p_4^rp_5^r(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_7|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^r(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)p_6^r(1 - p_7^r)](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (17)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(\mathbf{T}_8|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) &= [(1 - p_4^r)p_5^rp_6^r(1 - p_7^r) + p_4^r(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)p_7^r](1 - p_1)(1 - p_2)(1 \\
&\quad - p_3)p_4p_5p_6p_7 \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

The probability of the subtree \mathbf{T}_i is normalized by the probability of only one gene copy being retained for each species, which is equal to the sum $c = \sum_{i=1}^8 P^*(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$, i.e.,

$$P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = \frac{P^*(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)}{c} \quad (19)$$

Next, we calculate the probability distribution of gene trees for three different scenarios of gene loss. We consider the scenarios where gene loss occurs at the root, or in the internal branches, or in the terminal branches of the species tree.

C. Scenario 1: Gene loss occurs at the root of the species tree

C.1 The pectinate 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S1a)

If gene loss occurs at the root (i.e., $\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty$ and $p_1 = 1$), by equations 2-10 we have $P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i = 2, \dots, 8$. The probability distribution of a gene tree \mathbf{G} averaging over eight subtrees is given by

$$P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_1, \theta) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \quad (20)$$

Here $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ is the coalescent distribution of gene trees \mathbf{G} given the species tree \mathbf{S} and the population size parameters θ . This is expected because the retained copies after a loss at the root are orthologs and the corresponding gene tree follows the coalescent probability distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$. Thus, any consistent methods under the MSC are statistically consistent in estimating the species tree \mathbf{S} if gene loss occurs at the root of the species tree. But concatenation methods are statistically inconsistent if the species tree \mathbf{S} falls in the anomaly zone.

C.2 The symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a)

If gene loss occurs at the root (i.e., $\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty$ and $p_1 = 1$) of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a), equations 11-19 indicate that $P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i = 2, \dots, 8$. The probability distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} under the coalescent model with gene loss is equal to the coalescent distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ of a gene tree given the species tree \mathbf{S} , i.e., $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_1, \theta) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$. Thus, any consistent methods under the MSC are statistically consistent in estimating the symmetric 4-taxon species tree \mathbf{S} if gene loss occurs at the root of the species tree.

C.3 n-taxon species trees

The conclusions in B.1 and B.2 can be easily generalized to a species tree of more than 4 taxa. If gene loss occurs at the root (i.e., $\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty$ and $p_1 = 1$) of the n-taxon species tree, the retained copies (either the red copies or the green copies) after a loss at the root are orthologs and the corresponding gene tree follows the coalescent probability distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$. Thus, any

consistent methods under the MSC are statistically consistent in estimating the symmetric 4-taxon species tree \mathcal{S} if gene loss occurs at the root of the species tree.

D. Scenario 2: Gene loss occurs in an internal branch

D.1 The pectinate species tree (Fig. S1a)

There are two internal branches in the pectinate species tree \mathcal{S} (Fig. S1a). If gene loss occurs in the branch 2 and 7 (i.e., $\tau_2, \tau_7 \rightarrow \infty$ and $\tau_1 = 0$), we have $P(\mathbf{T}_2|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i \neq 2$. The probability distribution of gene trees \mathbf{G} averaging over eight subtrees is given by

$$P(\mathbf{G}|\mathcal{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_2, \theta) \quad (21)$$

Because \mathbf{T}_2 is topologically identical with the species tree \mathcal{S} , coalescent methods are statistically consistent in estimating the species tree \mathcal{S} . But concatenation methods are statistically inconsistent if the species tree \mathcal{S} falls in the anomaly zone and the duplication time t_1 (Fig. S1a) is small.

However, if gene loss occurs in the branch 3 (i.e., $\tau_3, \tau_6, \tau_7 \rightarrow \infty$ and $\tau_1, \tau_2 = 0$), we have $P(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i \neq 6$. The probability distribution of gene trees \mathbf{G} averaging over eight subtrees is given by

$$P(\mathbf{G}|\mathcal{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathcal{S}, \lambda) = P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_6, \theta) \quad (22)$$

Because \mathbf{T}_6 is incongruent with the species tree \mathcal{S} , both coalescent and concatenation methods are statistically inconsistent in estimating the species tree \mathcal{S} if gene loss occurs in the branch 3. In general, if the subtree \mathbf{T}_i induced by gene loss is incongruent with the species tree \mathcal{S} , species tree reconstruction methods consistently estimate the wrong tree \mathbf{T}_i .

D.2 The symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a)

For the symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a), gene loss in the two internal branches leads to the symmetric subtree T_6 (Fig. S2c), which is congruent with the symmetric species tree S . Thus, any consistent methods under the coalescent model are statistically consistent if gene loss occurs in the internal branches of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree. Because the symmetric subtree T_6 is not in the anomaly zone, concatenation methods are also statistically consistent if gene loss occurs in the internal branches of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree.

D.3 n-taxon species trees

In general, gene loss in the internal branches of an n-taxon species tree induces a unique subtree T^* with probability 1. Therefore, the probability distribution of gene trees under the coalescent model with gene loss is equal to the coalescent distribution of gene trees given the subtree T^* , i.e., $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^K P(\mathbf{G}|T_i, \theta)P(T_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = P(\mathbf{G}|T^*, \theta)$, where K is the number of subtrees induced by gene loss. If the subtree T^* is congruent with the species tree S , any consistent methods under the coalescent model are statistically consistent in estimating the species tree S . However, if the subtree T^* is incongruent with the species tree S , any consistent methods under the coalescent model are statistically inconsistent in estimating the species tree S .

E. Scenario 3: Gene loss occurs in the terminal branches

E.1 The pectinate 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S1a)

If gene loss occurs only in the terminal branches (i.e., $\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3 = 0$ and $\tau_4, \tau_5, \tau_6, \tau_7 > 0$) of the pectinate species tree (Fig. S1a) or the misidentification rates of paralog/ortholog programs are independent of each other across species, it indicates that gene copies are independently retained

for species A to D . Since $p_i = 1 - e^{-\tau_i} = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$, the probability of the subtree \mathbf{T}_i in equations 2-10 becomes

$$P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (23)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_2|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r) p_7^r \quad (24)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_3|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r (1 - p_6^r) p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r) p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) \quad (25)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_4|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r (1 - p_5^r) p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r (1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (26)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_5|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (27)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r) p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r p_5^r (1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (28)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_7|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r (1 - p_6^r) p_7^r + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r) p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) \quad (29)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_8|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r) p_7^r \quad (30)$$

If general, the probability $(p_4^r, p_5^r, p_6^r, p_7^r)$ that the red copy is lost in a terminal branch could be any number between 0 and 1, i.e., $0 \leq p_4^r, p_5^r, p_6^r, p_7^r \leq 1$. If all probabilities are equal to 1 or 0 (i.e., $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 1$ or $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 0$), the probability distribution of the subtree \mathbf{T} becomes $P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i = 2, \dots, 8$, leading to Scenario 1 described above. If $(p_4^r = p_5^r = 1, p_6^r = p_7^r = 0)$ or $(p_4^r = p_5^r = 0, p_6^r = p_7^r = 1)$, the probability distribution of the subtree \mathbf{T} becomes $P(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i \neq 6$, leading to Scenario 2 described above. If no probabilities are equal to 0 or 1 (i.e., $0 < p_4^r, p_5^r, p_6^r, p_7^r < 1$), then all 8 subtrees have a positive probability $0 < P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) < 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$.

E.2 The symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a)

If gene loss occurs in the terminal branches (i.e., $\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3 = 0$ and $\tau_4, \tau_5, \tau_6, \tau_7 > 0$) of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree (Fig. S2a), the corresponding 8 subtrees \mathbf{T}_i (Fig. S2C) has the same probability

$$P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (31)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_2|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r) p_7^r \quad (32)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_3|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r p_5^r (1 - p_6^r) p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r) p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) \quad (33)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_4|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = p_4^r (1 - p_5^r) p_6^r p_7^r + (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r (1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (34)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_5|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (35)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r)(1 - p_5^r) p_6^r p_7^r + p_4^r p_5^r (1 - p_6^r)(1 - p_7^r) \quad (36)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_7|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r (1 - p_6^r) p_7^r + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r) p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) \quad (37)$$

$$P(\mathbf{T}_8|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = (1 - p_4^r) p_5^r p_6^r (1 - p_7^r) + p_4^r (1 - p_5^r)(1 - p_6^r) p_7^r \quad (38)$$

If all probabilities are equal to 1 or 0 (i.e., $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 1$ or $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 0$), the probability distribution of the subtree \mathbf{T} becomes $P(\mathbf{T}_1|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i = 2, \dots, 8$, leading to Scenario 1 described above. If $(p_4^r = p_5^r = 1, p_6^r = p_7^r = 0)$ or $(p_4^r = p_5^r = 0, p_6^r = p_7^r = 1)$, the probability distribution of the subtree \mathbf{T} becomes $P(\mathbf{T}_6|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = 0$ for $i \neq 6$, leading to Scenario 2 described above. If no probabilities are equal to 0 or 1 (i.e., $0 < p_4^r, p_5^r, p_6^r, p_7^r < 1$), then all 8 subtrees have a positive probability $0 < P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) < 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$. Next, we focus on the cases where two copies (red and green) are equally likely to be lost, i.e., $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 0.5$.

E.3 The probability distribution of a gene tree \mathbf{G} if two copies are equally likely to be lost

If two copies (red and green) in the terminal branches of the species tree are equally likely to be lost, i.e., $p_4^r = p_5^r = p_6^r = p_7^r = 0.5$, the 8 subtrees for the pectinate or symmetric 4-taxon species tree are uniformly distributed with probabilities $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) = \frac{1}{8}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$ (see Eqn. 23-30 and 31-38). The lengths of the two internal branches of the species tree \mathbf{S} are denoted by w_1 and w_2 (in coalescent units), e.g., $w_1 = t_3/\theta_3$ and $w_2 = t_2/\theta_2$ where t_2 and t_3 are the

lengths of two internal branches of the species tree (Fig. S1a and Fig. S2a). We first consider the cases where the lengths of internal branches of the species tree are short (i.e., high ILS), i.e., $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0$.

Lemma 1: As $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0$, the probability distribution $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ of a gene tree \mathbf{G} given the 4-taxon species tree \mathbf{S} converges to

$$P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{18} & \text{for } \mathbf{G} = g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{12} \\ \frac{2}{18} & \text{for } \mathbf{G} = g_{13}, g_{14}, g_{15} \end{cases}.$$

Proof: As the lengths of two internal branches (i.e., w_1 and w_2) in a 4-taxon species tree \mathbf{S} (either pectinate or symmetrical) approach zero, the probability of the number of coalescence events $[0,0,3]$ converges to 1, i.e., $P(0,0,3) \rightarrow 1$, while the other probabilities $P(0,1,2)$, $P(1,0,2)$, and $P(1,1,1)$ converge to zero (see section E.1 and E.2). Thus, the probability of a gene tree $P(g_i|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \rightarrow \frac{1}{8}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$, and $P(g_i|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \rightarrow \frac{2}{8}$ for $i = 13, 14, 15$. ■

For the pectinate 4-taxon species tree $((A, B), C), D$, the probability of the gene tree g_1 is the highest among 12 pectinate gene trees, while the probability of the gene tree g_{13} is the highest among three symmetrical gene trees. If the probability of the gene tree g_{13} is greater than that of the gene tree g_1 , then the gene tree g_{13} is the most probable one. According to Lemma 1, as the lengths of the two internal branches approach zero, the probabilities of gene trees g_1 and g_{13} converge to $\frac{1}{18}$ and $\frac{2}{18}$, respectively. Thus, as $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0$, the gene tree g_{13} is the most probable one and the pectinate species tree is in the anomaly zone.

Theorem 1: As $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0$, the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence between the two

distributions $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda)$ and $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ converges to 0, i.e.,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) \rightarrow 0$$

Proof: By Eqn. 1, the probability $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda)$ is equal to $\sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$. As the lengths of two internal branches of the species tree \mathbf{S} decrease to 0, the lengths of two internal branches of any subtree \mathbf{T}_i for $i = 1, \dots, 8$ decrease to 0. Thus, as $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0$, by Lemma 1,

$$P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta) \rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{1}{18} & \text{for } \mathbf{G} = g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{12} \\ \frac{2}{18} & \text{for } \mathbf{G} = g_{13}, g_{14}, g_{15} \end{cases}$$

Since the gene tree topology has a discrete probability distribution, the KL divergence between the two distributions $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)$ and $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ is given by

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) = \sum_{j=1}^{15} P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \log \frac{P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(g_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0} D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) &= \lim_{w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0} \sum_{j=1}^{15} P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \log \frac{P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(g_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{15} \lim_{w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0} P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \times \lim_{w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0} \log \frac{P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(g_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The last equality holds because $\lim_{w_1, w_2 \rightarrow 0} \log \frac{P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(g_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} = 0$ according to Lemma 1. In addition,

since the probability $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$ is bounded, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^8 D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta))P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) \rightarrow 0.$$

Thus,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) = D_{\text{KL}}\left(\sum_{i=1}^8 P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)\right)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^8 D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta))P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) \rightarrow 0.$$

■

Theorem 2: Let \mathbf{S} be an n -taxon species tree with internal branch lengths $w_i = \frac{t_i}{\theta_i}, i = 1, \dots, n - 2$ in coalescent units. As $w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0$, the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence between the two distributions $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda)$ and $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ converges to 0, i.e.,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) \rightarrow 0$$

Proof: Let $P^*(\mathbf{G})$ be the coalescent distribution of gene trees in a single population. As the internal branch lengths of the species tree \mathbf{S} go to 0, all coalescence events occur in the root population of the species tree. Thus, As $w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0$, $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \rightarrow P^*(\mathbf{G})$. Let $\{\mathbf{T}_i, i = 1, \dots, K\}$ be the K subtrees induced by gene loss occurring along the lineages of the species tree \mathbf{S} . As the internal branch lengths of the species tree go to 0, i.e., $w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0$, the internal branch lengths of all subtrees $\{\mathbf{T}_i, i = 1, \dots, K\}$ converge to 0 as well. Thus, As $w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0$, $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta) \rightarrow P^*(\mathbf{G})$ for $i = 1, \dots, K$. Let $\{g_i, i = 1, \dots, M\}$ be the M gene trees. The KL divergence between the two distributions $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)$ and $P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)$ is given by

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) = \sum_{j=1}^M P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \log \frac{P(g_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(g_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) &= \lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} \sum_{j=1}^M P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \log \frac{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^M \lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta) \times \lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} \log \frac{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The last equality holds because $\lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} \log \frac{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} = \log \frac{\lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{S}, \theta)}{\lim_{w_1, \dots, w_{n-2} \rightarrow 0} P(\mathbf{g}_j|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta)} =$

$\log \frac{P^*(\mathbf{g}_j)}{P^*(\mathbf{g}_j)} = 0$. In addition, since the probability $P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda)$ is bounded, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^K D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) \rightarrow 0.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) &= D_{\text{KL}}\left(\sum_{i=1}^K P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta) P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)\right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^K D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{T}_i, \theta), P(\mathbf{G}|\mathbf{S}, \theta)) P(\mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \lambda) \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

■

When the internal branches in the species tree \mathbf{S} are long (i.e., a low level of ILS), i.e., $w_1, w_2 \rightarrow \infty$, the lengths of the two internal branches in the eight subtrees $\{\mathbf{T}_i, i = 1, \dots, 8\}$ should also be long. According to the coalescent theory, as the lengths of internal branches go to infinity, most of the gene trees \mathbf{G} generated from the subtree \mathbf{T}_i are congruent with \mathbf{T}_i itself, i.e., Thus, the probability distribution of gene trees \mathbf{G} for out-paralogs becomes

$$P(\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{T}_i|\mathbf{S}, \theta, \lambda) = \frac{1}{8} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, 8).$$

For this probability distribution of a gene tree \mathbf{G} , the following theorem shows that coalescent

methods are statistically consistent, i.e., coalescent methods accurately recover the true species tree as the number of sampled genes increases.

Theorem 3: If the probability distribution of gene trees is $P(\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{T}_i) = \frac{1}{8}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$, coalescent methods MP-EST (Liu et al. 2010) and STAR (Liu et al. 2009) are statistically consistent in estimating the 4-taxon species tree as the number of genes approaches infinity.

Proof: We first consider the pectinate 4-taxon species tree which induces 8 subtrees, i.e., $\mathbf{T}_1 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $\mathbf{T}_2 = (((A, B), C), D)$, $\mathbf{T}_3 = (((A, B), D), C)$, $\mathbf{T}_4 = (((A, C), D), B)$, $\mathbf{T}_5 = (((B, C), D), A)$, $\mathbf{T}_6 = ((A, B), (C, D))$, $\mathbf{T}_7 = ((A, C), (B, D))$, and $\mathbf{T}_8 = ((A, D), (B, C))$ (Fig. S1c).

(i) For MP-EST, if the probability distribution of a gene tree is $P(\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{T}_i) =$

$\frac{1}{8}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$), as the number of genes approaches infinity, the frequencies of triples converge

to

$$P(AB|C) = \frac{1}{2}, P(AC|B) = \frac{1}{4}, P(BC|A) = \frac{1}{4},$$

$$P(AB|D) = \frac{1}{2}, P(AD|B) = \frac{1}{4}, P(BD|A) = \frac{1}{4},$$

$$P(AC|D) = \frac{1}{2}, P(AD|C) = \frac{1}{4}, P(CD|A) = \frac{1}{4},$$

$$P(BC|D) = \frac{1}{2}, P(BD|C) = \frac{1}{4}, P(CD|B) = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Here, triples $\langle AB|C \rangle$, $\langle AB|D \rangle$, $\langle AC|D \rangle$, and $\langle BC|D \rangle$ maximize the pseudo-likelihood of the

MP-EST method. In addition, the true species tree $(((A, B), C), D)$ contains four triples $\langle AB|C \rangle$,

$\langle AB|D \rangle$, $\langle AC|D \rangle$, and $\langle BC|D \rangle$. Thus, as the number of genes approaches infinity, the MP-EST

tree converges to the true species tree. (ii) For STAR, if the probability distribution of gene trees

is $P(\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{T}_i) = \frac{1}{8}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$), the expected distance between species x and y is given by

$D(x, y) = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{i=1}^8 d_i(x, y)$ where $d_i(x, y)$ is the distance between x and y in subtree T_i . The 16 pairwise distances among 4 species A, B, C, D are given in the following matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{17}{8} & \frac{19}{8} & \frac{21}{8} \\ \frac{17}{8} & 0 & \frac{19}{8} & \frac{21}{8} \\ \frac{19}{8} & \frac{19}{8} & 0 & \frac{21}{8} \\ \frac{21}{8} & \frac{21}{8} & \frac{21}{8} & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

As the number of genes approaches infinity, the distance matrix converges to the expected distance matrix. In addition, the neighbor-joining (NJ) tree (Saitou and Nei 1987) for the expected distance matrix is $((A, B), C), D$. Therefore, as the number of genes approaches infinity, the true species tree can be statistically consistently estimated by the STAR method. (iii)

For ASTRAL, the true species tree $((A, B), C), D$ minimizes the tree distance between gene trees and the species tree if the distribution of gene trees is $P(\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{T}_i) = \frac{1}{8}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$).

Thus, the true species tree can be consistently estimated by ASTRAL. Similarly, we can show that MP-EST, STAR, ASTRAL are statistically consistent for the symmetric 4-taxon species tree.

■

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FIGURE S1. a) Gene loss occurs along the branches of the pectinate 4-taxon species tree. λ_1 is the loss rate at the root of the species tree and λ_i is the loss rate for the branch i of the species tree. b) A whole-genome duplication (WGD) occurs in the ancestral population at the root of the pectinate 4-taxon species tree \mathcal{S} . Here, t_2 and t_3 are the lengths of the two internal branches, and t_1 is the duplication time. The two major subclades of paralogs are highlighted in red and green, respectively. c) The topologies of eight subtrees for the species tree \mathcal{S} . The lengths of the two internal branches in a subtree are denoted by w_1 and w_2 (in coalescent units).

FIGURE S2. a) Gene loss occurs along the branches of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree. λ_1 is the loss rate at the root of the species tree and λ_i is the loss rate for the branch i of the species tree. b) A whole-genome duplication (WGD) occurs in the ancestral population at the root of the symmetric 4-taxon species tree \mathcal{S} . Here, t_2 and t_3 are the lengths of the two internal branches, and t_1 is the duplication time. The two major subclades of paralogs are highlighted in red and green, respectively. c) The topologies of eight subtrees for the species tree \mathcal{S} . The lengths of the two internal branches in a subtree are denoted by w_1 and w_2 (in coalescent units).

FIGURE S3. The mean *RF* distances between the true species tree and those inferred from data sets with simulated loss of paralogs. DNA sequences were simulated on species trees S_1 to S_4 (Fig. 2), and loss of paralogs was generated according to one of the 14 patterns as described in the Materials and Methods section. Species trees were then inferred from the 50- and 100-gene data sets using the alignment-based coalescent method (BPP).

Figure S4. The topologies of incorrect species trees inferred from simulated DNA data sets. a) The pectinate tree estimated by CA-MP for the pattern $\langle p_A = p_B = p_C = p_D = 1 \rangle$ when the true species tree is symmetric. b) The symmetric tree estimated by CA-ML when the true species tree is pectinate. c) The species tree estimated by ASTRAL, MP-EST, and STAR for the pattern $\langle p_A = p_C = 1, p_B = p_D = \frac{1}{2} \rangle$. d) The species tree estimated by MP-EST for the pattern $\langle p_A = p_C = 1, p_B = p_D = \frac{1}{2} \rangle$. e) The species tree estimated by MP-EST for the pattern $\langle p_A = p_D = 1, p_B = p_C = \frac{1}{2} \rangle$